

Grain quality

Calorific values of 60 rice varieties

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We determined the calorific values of 60 rice varieties (30 hybrid derivatives, 28 traditional, and 2 improved varieties) in raw and parboiled forms (see table).

Calories significantly differed among the varieties. In raw rice, traditional variety Aryankali had the highest value (371 kcal) and the hybrid derivative Bhadra, the lowest (279 kcal). We observed a significant variation in calories in all rice

varieties after parboiling, with Aryankali again having the highest calorific value

(383 kcal) and Bhadra, the lowest (301 kcal). ■

Calorific values of 60 rice varieties.

Variety	Raw rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Parboiled rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Variety	Raw rice (kcal g ⁻¹)	Parboiled rice (kcal g ⁻¹)
Kavungin-poothala	330	357	Thrissur local 2	312	333
Veluthavattan	317	337	Ponnaryan	332	348
Kattamodan	342	380	Chuvannari Thavalakannan	336	356
Arvan	345	375	Veluthari Thavalakannan	346	359
Vadakken Chitteni	307	358	Thkkencheera	357	365
Thekken	345	353	Cheriya Aryan	316	364
Chenkayama	342	345	Aruvakkari	348	354
Chuvannamodan	321	329	Kutticheradi	344	356
Elappapoochemban	335	372	Sinduram	316	373
Navara	341	358	<i>Improved</i>		
Thrissur local 1	312	333	CO 25	341	358
			Mashuri	332	362

Cibodas, a high-yielding variety with good grain quality

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B9775b-Mr-8-1-1 (derived from the cross B7004d-Mr-10-1/B6992f-Mr-262) is a

high-yielding line with good grain quality. Released as Cibodas for the irrigated rice ecosystem in Sep 1995, the variety is resistant to brown planthopper biotype 1 and bacterial blight strain III. It yields about 30% more than IR64 and Cisadane at 200- to 500-m above sea level (Table 1). Cibodas seems more suitable for cropping on intermediate elevation (about 400 m).

We compared grain quality characteristics of Cibodas with those of IR64 and Cisadane (Table 2). Large grain size (1,000-grain weight = 349) probably contributes to the variety's high yield potential. Cibodas has intermediate amylose content and tender cooking quality that rice consumers in Java prefer. ■

Table 1. Average yield of Cibodas in seven provinces in Indonesia. 1993-95.

Province	Locations (no.)	Elevation (m)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Increase over check (%) ^a
Jakarta	1	50	5.7	2 a
West Java	3	200-450	8.2	30 b
West Java	3	400-600	7.0	29 a
Central Java	3	2-18	5.8	12 a
East Java	1	86	6.2	5 a
Lampung	1	750	6.3	14 a
Bengkulu	1	320	6.9	12 a

^a a = IR64, b = Cisadane.

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics of Cibodas, IR64, and Cisadane.

Characteristic	Cibodas	IR64	Cisadane
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	5.7 - 8.2	3.8 - 6.2	4.8 - 7.8
Plant height (cm)	115	99	110
Days to maturity	123	115	135
1,000-grain weight (g)	34	25	28
Head rice recovery (%)	80	80	80
Grain length (mm)	6.5	7.0	6.7
Grain length-breadth ratio	2.4	3.2	2.6
Amylose content	24	22	20
Cooking quality	Tender	Tender	Tender

Improving provitamin A (carotenoid) content of rice endosperm

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Genetic engineering is a feasible approach to alter or improve carotenoid content of endosperm, an agronomically valuable tissue. However, to plan a strategy for engineering rice endosperm, we must identify the biosynthetic block preventing carotenoid accumulation. Three alternative possibilities are being considered: 1) genes encoding one or more of the biosynthetic enzymes may not be expressed in the endosperm, 2) these enzymes are expressed but are not functional, and/or 3) a limitation

1. RT-PCR analysis: PSY and PDS transcribed throughout rice endosperm development. ^a M = mature endosperm. ^b DAF = days after flowering. ^c Sh = Sucrose synthetase.

exists in precursors available to the pathway. Rice endosperm lacks both end products of the carotenoid biosynthetic pathway and any intermediates, suggesting that biosynthetic enzymes may not be expressed. Only geranylgeranyl diphosphate (GGPP), a substrate of the first enzyme specific to the carotenoid biosynthetic pathway, is present. GGPP is a precursor common to other pathways, such as the gibberellic acid biosynthetic pathway.

We developed gene and protein probes to test the expression of the PSY and PDS, the first two enzymes specific to the pathway. Genes encoding both enzymes were each mapped to a single genetic locus in rice and in maize and behaved as single

copy genes by Southern blot analysis. Reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction showed transcripts in the leaves and endosperm. In developing rice endosperm, the PSY transcript was constant, whereas the PDS transcript increased over time (Fig. 1). Using a polyclonal antiserum raised against maize PSY, Western blot analysis showed PSY to be constantly expressed in developing rice endosperm (Fig. 2). We used a starch gene encoding sucrose synthetase to compare the transcript and protein analyses. Finally, high-pressure liquid chromatography analysis of a rice carotenoid mutant showed phytoene (a carotenoid intermediate) in the leaves and embryos but not in the endosperm.

2. Western blot analysis: PSY protein expressed throughout rice endosperm development.

Several factors likely cause the carotenoid deficiency in rice. Genes encoding PSY and PDS, the first two biosynthetic enzymes, are expressed in developing rice endosperm. However, the absence of intermediates, even in rice mutants blocked in the pathway, suggests that the endosperm PSY does not function or that precursors feeding the pathway are limiting. Also, the level of PDS transcripts was not constant, suggesting the possibility of discordant expression of enzymes at inappropriate levels or times during endosperm development, which would contribute to the general problem of carotenoid deficiency. ■

Phytoene-forming activities in wild-type and transformed rice endosperm

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Rice endosperm does not contain carotene, including phytoene, the first carotene in the biosynthetic pathway. To develop a strategy for rice transformation with the aim

of obtaining phytoene synthesis in endosperm (as a first step toward **b**-carotene accumulation), we investigated in initial experiments the enzymatic prenyl lipid-forming activity of this tissue. We incubated immature endosperm with [1-¹⁴C]isopentenyl diphosphate and [¹⁴C]geranylgeranyldiphosphate (GGPP). After hydrolysis with alkaline phosphatase to convert prenyl phosphates into their corresponding alcohols, followed by extraction, reverse phase-high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) analysis revealed farnesol, geranylgeraniol, a third unidentified alcohol, and squalene as the main products in incubations with radio-labeled isopentenyl diphosphate.

Geranyl-geraniol was most important because its diphosphate, besides being a substrate in the formation of various prenyl lipids, is also the first carotenoid-specific precursor—the substrate of the enzyme phytoene synthase. Both phytoene synthase and GGPP are localized in the plastids of plants.

We cloned a cDNA coding for phytoene synthase from the flower *Narcissus pseudonarcissus* and proved its identity by functional expression (enzymatic activity) in insect cells, using the baculovirus system. To confirm the presence of functional transit sequence, we studied the import of a radio-labeled in vitro translation product into isolated pea chloroplasts.